

USE OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THINK-PAIR-SHARE (TPS) STRATEGY ON STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN GRADE 12 GENERAL BIOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Generative AI in the Think-Pair-Share strategy is an innovative approach that fosters collaboration and deeper understanding through reflection, peer interaction, and critical analysis. One notable example of Generative AI is ChatGPT. This study was conducted to determine the effects of the ChatGPT-Think-Pair-Share strategy on students' critical thinking skills in Grade 12 general biology at Mindanao State University-Wao Community High School during the first quarter of the SY 2024-2025. The study employed a quasi-experimental design where two (2) intact sections were selected: 42 participants in the ChatGPT-TPS and 40 in the NonChatGPT-TPS. An adopted critical thinking essay test rubric was administered. Data were analyzed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation. Results revealed that the critical thinking skills of students were Average when exposed to the ChatGPT-TPS strategy. In contrast, students in the NonChatGPT-TPS group remained at a Deficient level after the intervention. Moreover, the ANCOVA results revealed a significant difference in students' critical thinking skills. With these findings, teachers may integrate the ChatGPT-TPS strategy routinely in the actual classroom setting, particularly in general biology, to enhance students' critical thinking skills.

Keywords: *ChatGPT, critical thinking skills, think-pair-share*

INTRODUCTION

ChatGPT is one of the notable advancements in Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI). Its capacity to deliver immediate personalized feedback, efficient task management, and promote active learning provides an avenue for its potential application in education. This necessitates engaging in conversations supported by empirical and data-driven insights to prepare us for AI's evolving role in shaping the future of learning.

In the Philippines, science education has long been a challenge. A recent Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) study revealed that only 23% of Filipino learners, as opposed to the 76% OECD average, can correctly explain basic scientific phenomena (OECD, 2023). National Achievement Test results also indicate persistently low performance in both science and math from 2004 to 2018 (Lumbay & Mangansat, 2022). In the Bangsamoro region, the Functional Literacy, Education, and Mass Media Survey (FLEMMS) reported that BARMM's basic literacy rate is 83.2%, the lowest among all Philippine regions (Second Congressional Commission on Education, 2025). At Mindanao State University-Wao Community High School, most students, especially those in the lower sections, continue to struggle with understanding science concepts, as reflected in their Mean Percentage Score, which consistently falls below the passing score.

Furthermore, Mahanal et al. (2017) found that students with higher academic ability develop better critical thinking skills than those with lower academic ability. Hence, our current low academic achievement significantly affects the development of students' critical thinking skills, which are essential for functioning in the world of work and a knowledge-based society. With the advancement of technology and the constant changes in the global landscape, critical thinking skills (CTS) are increasingly seen as a valuable asset for graduates. These skills enable them to adapt to technological advancements and enhance their prospects for employability (Fadhlullah & Ahmad, 2017). Given these, critical thinking skills should be given priority in education (Utami et al., 2017).

To address these challenges, more robust instructional strategies are needed that foster the critical thinking process. The Think-Pair-Share (TPS) strategy is a collaborative teaching technique that is proven to promote critical thinking skills (Fauzi et al., 2021; Salim & Disman, 2023) and enhance academic achievement in science (Ogbaga & Osuafor, 2023). Moreover, ChatGPT can improve learning outcomes (Graefen & Fazal, 2023), support inquiry-based learning (Adarkwah et al., 2023), promote active and personalized feedback (Baidoo-anu & Ansah, 2023), and serve as a virtual tutor (Nguyen et al., 2023). Currently, very few studies have been conducted that integrate the TPS strategy and ChatGPT. This integration will enable teachers to utilize ChatGPT to enhance students' critical thinking skills, thereby improving their academic abilities in science.

This study aimed to examine the effectiveness of ChatGPT in a Think-Pair-Share strategy in fostering critical thinking skills in Grade 12 general biology. The findings of this study will provide scientific and benchmark information to the curriculum planners,

policymakers, school administrators, and teachers in meaningfully integrating Artificial Intelligence, such as ChatGPT, for the enhancement, revision, and contextualization of scientific literacy and to meet the global demands of 21st-century science education.

Research Questions

This research aimed to investigate the effects of ChatGPT in a Think-Pair-Share (TPS) Strategy on students' critical thinking skills and academic achievement in Grade 12 General Biology. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of critical thinking skills of students exposed to the ChatGPT-TPS Strategy and those exposed to the NonChatGPT-TPS Strategy, in terms of:
 - a. Pretest; and
 - b. Posttest
2. Is there a significant difference between students' critical thinking skills when exposed to the ChatGPT-TPS Strategy and those exposed to the NonChatGPT-TPS Strategy.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quasi-experimental design to explore the effects of using ChatGPT in a Think-Pair-Share Strategy on students' critical thinking skills. In this regard, two (2) groups with 42 (ChatGPT-TPS) and 40 (NonChatGPT-TPS) students were compared. The ChatGPT-TPS utilized a 7-E learning cycle, with most of the stages reinforced with ChatGPT. The integration of ChatGPT and the Think-Pair-Share-Strategy was during the elaboration stage. The stages of the implementation of the ChatGPT-Think Pair share strategy were adapted in the study of Bitzenbauer (2023), inspired by Alsmadi et al. (2023), Lyman (1981), and Prah (2017). In the Non-ChatGPT-TPS, A 7E Learning cycle was also utilized to teach desired concepts. The regular use of video simulations, PowerPoint presentations, Hands-on laboratory experiments, and activities found in the DepEd Learner's material was implemented.

This study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Wao Community High School, Wao, Lanao Del Sur. The researcher developed a Four (4) item essay test to evaluate students' critical thinking skills. The test covers the topics in The Cell, Cell Cycle, and Transport Mechanism. Bloom's Taxonomy of higher-order thinking skills, mainly focusing on analyzing, evaluating, and creating, serves as the foundation for the questionnaire construction. The test questionnaire consisted of two (2) items for analyzing, two (1) items for evaluating, and one (1) item for creating. The instrument was then validated by experts for reliability.

The questionnaire was administered to the two groups before and after the intervention was given. A Critical Thinking Embedded Essay Test Rubric developed by

Finken and Ennis (1993) and later modified by Zubaidah et al. (2015) was used to evaluate students' responses. The rubric has five (5) indicators: 1. Focus, 2. Reasoning (reason or idea), 3. Organization (way of thinking), 4. Convention (grammar), and 5. Integration. Each of the five features is rated on a 5-point scale. The total score can range from 0 to 25 points.

In order to determine the students' critical thinking skills, basic descriptive statistical tools like percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to analyze the data from critical thinking test. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was also used to examine if there is a significant difference in students' critical thinking skills when exposed to ChatGPT-TPS and NonChatGPT-TPS.

RESULTS

Table 1. Students' critical thinking skills in terms of pretest and posttest.

		Pretest				Posttest				Qualitative Interpretation
Raw Score	Percentage Equivalent	ChatGPT-TPS		Non-ChatGPT-TPS		ChatGPT-TPS		Non-ChatGPT-TPS		
		(n=42)		(n=40)		(n=42)		(n=40)		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
90-100	90-100	0	0	0	0	11	26.2	0	0	Exemplary
85-89	85-89	0	0	0	0	10	23.82	0	0	Above Average
80-84	80-84	0	0	0	0	5	11.9	1	2.5	Average
75-79	75-79	0	0	0	0	9	21.43	3	7.5	Below Average
74-below	74-below	42	100	40	100	7	16.67	36	90	Deficient
Total		42	100	40	100	42	100	40	100	
Overall MPS		38.57		42.76		82.71		52.50		
QI		Deficient		Deficient		Average		Deficient		

Legend:

Percentage Equivalent	Description	Qualitative Interpretation
90%-100%	Outstanding	Exemplary
85%-89%	Very Satisfactory	Above Average
80%-84%	Satisfactory	Average
75%-79%	Fair	Below Average
74%-below	Needs Improvement	Deficient

Table 2. Students' critical thinking skills in Posttest

Group	N	Mean	SD
ChatGPT-TPS	42	82.7143	11.60169
NonChatGPT-TPS	40	52.5000	9.15115
TOTAL	82	67.9756	18.42166

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	399305.714 ^a	3	133101.905	1485.536	.000**	
Pretest (Covariate)	1706.286	1	1706.286	19.044	.000**	0.194
Group	37226.624	2	18613.312	207.741	.000**	0.840
Error	7078.286	79	89.599			

TOTAL	406384.000	82
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**Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

DISCUSSION

Table 1 demonstrates that both groups exhibited similarly low critical thinking skills during the pretest, with an overall mean percentage score (MPS) of 38.57% for the ChatGPT-TPS group and 42.76% for the NonChatGPT-TPS group. These scores were qualitatively categorized as *Deficient*. In the post-test, the ChatGPT-TPS group showed improvement, with 35 students (83.83%) scoring above the minimum passing score. Specifically, 11 students (26.2%) were categorized as *Exemplary*, 10 (23.82%) as *Above Average*, 5 (11.9%) as *Average*, 9 (21.43%) as *Below Average*, and 7 (16.67%) in the *Below Average* category. This improvement is reflected in the mean percentage score (MPS), rising from 38.57% to 82.71%, which is qualitatively interpreted as *Average*.

In contrast, the NonChatGPT-TPS group showed slight improvement, with only 4 participants (10%) scoring above the minimum passing score, while the majority (36 or 90%) remained in the *Deficient* category. The substantial increase, as reflected in the pretest mean percentage score (MPS) of 38.57% (*Deficient*) to a post-test MPS of 82.71% (*Average*), with 83.83% of students surpassing the minimum passing score. This may be due to how the ChatGPT-TPS strategy was designed to maximize students' active participation. By requiring students to critically assess ChatGPT's responses, the intervention transformed AI from a mere tool for generating answers into an interactive partner in the learning process. This is further strengthened by the Think-Pair-Share strategy where it allows students to work with their peers, providing an avenue to engage in deeper learning through knowledge sharing about the topic.

These findings emphasize that integrating AI tools like ChatGPT into collaborative learning frameworks such as the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) strategy enhances students' critical thinking skills. This suggests that AI-assisted technologies like the ChatGPT do not necessarily hinder the development of students' critical thinking skills, contrary to some previous studies, if the following conditions are met: (1) they are integrated within structured pedagogical frameworks like TPS, which promote active learning through peer collaboration, dialogue, and reflection, and (2) they are employed in a manner that ensures students remain active participants in the learning process, engaging in higher-order cognitive tasks such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation rather than passive recipients of information.

The findings negate previous findings of Johnson (2020) as cited in de Sousa Saldanha and da Costa (2024) where he argued that AI personalized learning may harm critical thinking and creativity in a way that it will be reduced into algorithmic responses without the capacity for in depth learning. Furthermore, the results align with Ekuinam et al. (2024) where active engagement of students in using ChatGPT can increase students' critical thinking skills. Deng and Yu (2023) also espoused that students' critical thinking skills may be developed, especially with AI and ICT tools. Further, in Nurhayti's (2017)

and Tanner's (2017) research, the Think-Pair-Share strategy allows students to engage in deeper thinking because they are given enough processing time to respond, reflect, and assist one another. A study conducted by Fauzi et al. (2021) showed that TPS is more effective in developing students' critical thinking skills than the traditional method.

Table 2 shows the ANCOVA results for critical thinking between the ChatGPT-TPS and NonChatGPT-TPS groups. The ChatGPT-TPS group achieved a higher mean score ($M = 82.71$, $SD = 11.60$) compared to the NonChatGPT-TPS group ($M = 52.50$, $SD = 9.15$). The group effect ($F=207.741$, $p<0.000$) indicates that the intervention (ChatGPT-TPS) had a significant and substantial impact on students' critical thinking skills compared to the traditional method (NonChatGPT-TPS).

The interaction between students and ChatGPT encourages them to think critically and make informed judgments about whether to challenge or support ChatGPT's responses based on their existing knowledge of the topic.

For instance, during the Pair phase of the Think-Pair-Share strategy, ChatGPT was used to generate initial responses to student questions. These responses were not regarded as definitive answers. Instead, students were encouraged to assess ChatGPT's output critically for completeness and accuracy. For example, ChatGPT provided an incomplete explanation about what would happen if the carrier proteins that transport glucose are impaired or damaged. The students noted that ChatGPT's response was informative but lacked a detailed explanation of different GLUT proteins' specific mechanisms and roles and how tissues adapt. They were able to address this gap during the sharing phase, where students provided more detailed information from research journals. This engagement, where students interact with peers, compare ChatGPT-generated outputs, and critically evaluate its responses, fosters deeper learning by showing formative use and promoting the development of critical thinking rather than passive consumption.

The findings suggest that educators may integrate ChatGPT and the Think-Pair-Share strategy to foster critical thinking skills. Teaching students how to critically engage with AI-generated content and supplement it with information from reliable sources nurtures students to become independent learners and prepares them for a future where critical thinking and digital literacy are indispensable. To ensure its seamless implementation, educators must see to it that students know how to cite information from different sources and assist them in navigating various research databases.

These findings are coherent with Vygotsky's (1978) Social Constructivist Approach. The ChatGPT-TPS framework enhances students' critical thinking skills because it promotes peer collaboration while accentuating the combination of senses, prior knowledge, and new information to build new meaning and understanding based on authentic, cooperative, and reflective approaches.

These findings are also supported by Guo and Lee (2023) where ChatGPT was found to enhance students' critical thinking abilities, especially in formulating incisive and

probing questions, evaluating information to draw logical conclusions, and understanding complex subject matter. Liu et al. (2022) further revealed that the utilization of emerging technologies, such as chatbot systems, provides an avenue for students to think and make informed judgments, thereby fostering the habit of critical thinking. Consequently, these refute the previous findings of Firat (2023) and Salim et al. (2023), where reliance on ChatGPT may hinder the development of students' critical thinking skills.

Conclusions

The study's findings led to the following conclusions:

Students exposed to the ChatGPT-TPS strategy exhibited "average" critical thinking skills. While the NonChatGPT-TPS had very low critical thinking skills and were classified under the "deficient" category.

There is a significant difference between students' Critical Thinking Skills as exposed to ChatGPT-TPS and those in NonChatGPT-TPS.

Recommendations

The results of the study suggest the following recommendations:

Science teachers may start integrating the ChatGPT-TPS strategy in contextualizing their lesson delivery in general biology to foster student-centered collaborative learning.

School Principals may include AI-driven pedagogies such as ChatGPT-TPS strategy in planning and conducting their In-Service Training (INSET) and School Learning Action Cell (SLAC).

Curriculum Planners may also consider the inclusion of the ChatGPT-TPS strategy into the curriculum by establishing training and workshops that will help educators effectively use AI tools like ChatGPT within active learning strategies such as TPS.

Future researchers may explore different active learning strategies will improve students' critical thinking skills beyond average level.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Several measures were employed by the researcher to safeguard the integrity, rights, and information of the participants. Before the conduct of the study, a permit was secured from the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) of the institution. Letters of permission were also given to the school principal, teachers, and content validators. Parents' consent was also given to ensure students' voluntary participation in the study. During the entire research process, the participants were informed of what the research was about and what was expected of them to ensure voluntary participation. The

participants may cease to participate in the research process at any time without any consequence. Anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' information, except for the name of the locale of the study, are strictly observed about the Data Privacy Act of 2018.

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